

MEDICAL INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN INFECTIOUS DISEASES

Sherko'zieva G.F., Toshpulatov B.M.,

Fayziyev O'.Q., Bahriddinova M.N

Tashkent State Medical University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract. Religious culture is a solid foundation for the future of society. Infectious diseases can be transmitted from person to person, from animal to person, through food, water or air. When the spread of infectious diseases among the population was studied through a questionnaire, 33 (27.5%) of them answered the question “What infectious disease have you had?” - influenza, 8 (6.6%) - hepatitis, 12 (10.0%) - measles, 62 (51.6%) - Covid-19 and 5 (4.1%) - botulism. The results show that the largest number of participants indicated that they had been infected with Covid-19, that is, 62 out of a total of 120 participants (51.6%).

Keywords: population, health, infection, disease, poisoning, infectious diseases

Relevance. Infectious diseases are diseases caused by microorganisms, bacteria, viruses, fungi, or parasites. These microorganisms enter the human body and multiply there, causing a variety of symptoms and complications. Infectious diseases can be transmitted from person to person, from animal to person, through food, water, or air [4]. There are many types of infectious diseases, including bacterial infections, viral infections, fungal infections, and parasitic infections [3]. The symptoms of infectious diseases vary depending on the type and cause of the disease. Common symptoms include: fever, inflammation and pain, cough and sore throat, fatigue and headache, skin rashes or sores.

Today, the most important and urgent issue is to carry out active, useful work

to preserve human health and to improve the medical culture of our people. The improvement of medical culture in society is achieved by increasing both material and spiritual attention to medical science and implementing the results of fundamental and scientific-innovative research[5.6].

Purpose of the study. Based on the above, we conducted a survey to increase the medical literacy of the population and determine what information they have on preventing the spread of infectious diseases in order to strengthen prevention of seasonal infectious diseases among the population, and analyzed the results.

The object of the study.To determine the medical literacy of the population, a survey was conducted in various groups, and the survey included 44 citizens of the Syrdarya regional Zarshunoslik MFY, 17 students of the Syrdarya Abu Ali Ibn Sino Public Health Technical School of Syrdarya region, 23 students of the Syrdarya regional Zarshunoslik MFY School No. 10, and 36 people of different ages and professions who participated in the electronic survey via telegram groups. In total, a survey was conducted with 120 participants.

Results obtained. As a result of effective preventive and anti-epidemic measures implemented in our country, quarantine and extremely dangerous infectious diseases such as plague, cholera, yellow fever, viral hemorrhagic fevers, avian influenza, etc., are being prevented from entering the territory of the republic from abroad and spreading among the population. However, due to insufficient knowledge of our citizens about these diseases, diseases such as rabies, anthrax, and Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever have been registered among the population in recent years. Since compliance with sanitary and hygienic rules is of great importance in the prevention of infectious diseases, we obtained the following results in this questionnaire. When asked in the questionnaire whether they have information about caring for patients with infectious diseases, the respondents who participated in the questionnaire answered as follows: 33 (27.5%) participants - yes, 87 (72.5%) - no, which indicates that most of them do not know how to care for

patients. When asked if they can provide information about infectious diseases to their loved ones, 14 (11.6%) participants - yes, 106 (88.3%) - no (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Questionnaire question: Can you provide information about infectious diseases to your loved ones?

When we examined the prevalence of infectious diseases among the population, to the question "What infectious disease have you been infected with?", 33 (27.5%) reported having been infected with influenza, 8 (6.6%) with hepatitis, 12 (10.0%) with measles, 62 (51.6%) with Covid-19, and 5 (4.1%) with botulism. The results show that the majority of participants reported having been infected with Covid-19, that is, 62 out of a total of 120 participants (51.6%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2 “What infectious disease do you have?” answers to the question

Medical culture is a solid foundation for the future of society. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary for young people to understand the need to have a medical culture and approach it with determination, self-confidence and responsibility, pay serious attention to mastering medical knowledge, become more familiar with the theory and practice of medical activity, and be able to connect knowledge with life and practice. At the same time, it is very important to observe the rules of sanitation and hygiene in the prevention of infectious diseases. Proper washing and disinfection of hands, proper cooking and storage of food, receiving vaccines, wearing masks in public places and maintaining social distance, and using clean water and food sources are of particular importance. In addition to carrying out explanatory work among the population, there are tasks and tasks to be carried out in medical institutions in the treatment and prevention institutions of the health care system on the basis of SanQa M on the prevention and control of infectious diseases. Of course, if we follow the saying among our people that everyone is their own doctor, then it is in line with the goal that a person should first protect

themselves, observe cleanliness, and adhere to personal hygiene requirements.

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